

This a reference document referred to the CleanSky2 H2020 project [E-TSIN](#): Modular, scalable, multi-functional, high power density power controller for electrical taxi: In this paper, Field Weakening problematical is observed experimentally and finally corrected for high speed operation with an aeronautical PMSM.

As a context, E-TSIN proposal, presented by Indra Sistemas and CEIT jointly, try to answer in the best way the call JTI-CS2-2014-CFP01-SYS-02-02.

The referred call and this associated proposal are framed inside of the packet 4.1.2.4 (Modular power controller for advanced landing system) of the System ITD for the Cleansky2 project. This project will develop a next generation power controller for electric taxi. This controller shall feature increased power density, bidirectional power conversion, modularity, scalability, and multifunctionality to support wide range of aircraft applications. Inside this global project of aircraft electrical moving on ground (e-TAXI), this concrete WP, try to answer the necessity of electrical power converters to:

- Supply new electrical motors inside of the landing gear system (getting energy from electrical sources inside the aircraft)
- Re-charge dedicated batteries inside the aircraft for the landing gear system. This function will help to have additional power available in batteries to be used when necessary, as in acceleration moments. Moreover, the re-charge will be done when aircraft speed on ground is enough or there is a necessity of braking (producing electrical braking over the motors).

Then, proposal solution in this call develops a solution answering both functions and getting a global optimization of the system. This solution is done in accordance with aeronautical standards (environmental constrains), where the participants in this proposal have a vast experience.

This proposal is presented by the consortium INDRA & CEIT that have all competences and skills to develop this project in time and performances, based in its experience in bidirectional and modular power electronic converters and well-known aeronautic standards, rules and process, more when Indra base its business in manufacturing of aeronautic equipment and system, totally verified and qualified.

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Field Weakening Analysis on an Aeronautical PMSM under Field Oriented Control

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Abstract—This paper shows an experimental analysis and observation on Field Weakening (FW) problematical when Field Oriented Control (FOC) and Space Vector Modulation (SVM) are implemented on a Voltage Source Inverter (VSI) feeding an aeronautical Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) for eTAXI applications at high speed operation. Control strategy instability is first observed when (FW) entrance should be demanded at a certain speed-torque operation point. This critical point is analytically described and related to the experiments so that a control optimization can be finally implemented in the FOC algorithm. Effects on FW implementation are then presented for optimal performance of the system.

Index Terms—FOC, PMSM, Field Weakening, SVM

I. INTRODUCTION

FW is a well-known effect on PMSM control implementation. In essence, internal EMF of the motor increases with the speed in proportion. This is unproblematic in constant torque operation until the speed rises so that the voltage limit of the associated converter reaches its maximum value, which increases as the speed increases. When the speed increases, magnets flux make the stator voltage to increase to values much higher than those allowed by the machine and the converter. Then, entering the FW operation zone, the internal voltage has to be adjusted to be compatible with the applied converter voltage. This can be achieved, apart from modifying the motor magnetic design, by the modification on the d-axis current component in a FOC control algorithm, obtaining a leading motor power factor operation.

Figure 1 FOC block diagram. Ref: MATLAB/Simulink Solutions webpage

Figure 2 Field Weakening Voltage Constraints. Ref: FOC PMSM TI notes

For a specific torque operation point, maximum speed (base speed, ω_b) operation without FW entrance can be analytically evaluated taking into consideration the condition for FW need, that is, maximum converter output voltage limitation, V_{max} . In a classical DCAC Voltage Source Inverter, this maximum voltage is related to the input DC voltage.

$$v_d^2 + v_q^2 = V_{max}^2 = V_{dc} / \sqrt{3} \quad (1)$$

In a PMSM with voltage and currents referred to a ω_e (electrical speed) speed rotating reference frame

$$v_d = i_d \cdot R_s - \omega_e L_d L_q + L_d \frac{di_d}{dt} \quad (2)$$

$$v_q = i_q \cdot R_s + \omega_e L_d L_q + \omega_e \Psi_m + L_q \frac{di_q}{dt} \quad (3)$$

At base speed operation point, derivatives are null in steady state and i_d is still null also. So, simplifying (2) and (3) and evaluating then (1), an expression for base speed can be obtained if i_q can be related to the operating point electromagnetic torque, T_e .

In a non-salient pole PMSM, T_e can be expressed in terms of i_q , the machine poles and the magnets flux, as follows:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} \cdot P \cdot \Psi_m \cdot i_q \rightarrow i_q(T_e \text{ operation point}) \rightarrow N_b(T_e \text{ operation point}) \quad (1)$$

Figure 3 Field Weakening base speed for a certain operation torque

II. FW STRATEGY

Considering a FOC control strategy for a DCAC VSI like the block diagram in Figure 1, a simple FW strategy can be implemented in order to perform extended speed operation for the machine.

As VSI output maximum voltage can't be overpassed, if maximum voltage is nearly observed the i_d component for the current control can be modified accordingly so that the torque can be followed at that speed. i_d ref changes from zero to a negative value in order to maintain maximum voltage and get the torque.

Figure 4 Field Weakening function diagram. Reference: FOC PMSM TI notes

Stator voltage modulus is evaluated in dq reference frame and then compared to the maximum that a VSI can perform. Result is saturated to 0 in order to keep $i_d=0$ until FW is needed because maximum voltage has been reached. Negative i_d ref is generated for the current control if maximum voltage is reached.

i_{qref} component has to be evaluated in order not to overpass maximum allowed current in the motor.

III. FW SIMULATION

A model of a VSI controlling a PMSM by means of FOC in Figure 1 has been implemented but with no FW strategy. Results from increasing the speed at a certain torque level are analyzed. Increasing and decreasing speed ramps are imposed at a certain torque level.

Figure 5 No FW algorithm implementation in the control

It can be clearly observed in Figure 5 that current control can't be maintained in the machine when a specific speed is reached for the evaluated torque operation. When the speed decreases from base speed for that torque, control is recovered.

When FW loop is enabled on the control algorithm, performance changes. It can be observed that control is permanently achieved over the PMSM at any speed for the evaluated torque.

Figure 6 FW algorithm implementation in the control

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Same control loss can be observed experimentally when equivalent fixed speed test is performed under torque control. For an imposed ramp speed profile, control is lost above a certain speed and recovered afterwards when it is decreased below this.

Figure 7 Fixed speed test-Torque control without FW

FW need is also observed in speed control tests when a speed above base speed is demanded to the control. It can be observed that control is not lost, but demanded reference is not obtained and demanded current is saturated to its maximum.

Figure 8 Speed control test without FW-need to FW when $n_{ref}=500rpm$ (not reached)

When FW algorithm is implemented in the control, higher speeds are reached in a controlled way. i_d and i_q ref derived currents behave as expected: negative values for i_d and not saturated and continuous for i_q according to demanded torque.

V. CONCLUSION

Field Weakening experimental observation and implementation has been discussed in this paper. From analytical analysis for base speed definition and feedback compensation strategy, simulation scenarios have been analyzed in order to observe the impact on non-FW operation on the system performance. This unregulated performance has also been observed and verified from simulations in experimental tests so that next FW implementation on the control could lead to its correction.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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